

INFLUENCE OF Z-PINNING ON IN-PLANE SHEAR PROPERTIES; DAMAGE AND LOCAL STRAIN VARIATION

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SUMMARY

Z pins improve resistance to delamination and are known to affect tensile and compression properties, but little work has been performed on in-plane shear. They are shown here to reduce the apparent in-plane shear modulus and strength of carbon/epoxy laminates. Z-pins modify the strain field measured by full-field image analysis in specimens and slow damage development, but create a new damage mechanism.

Keywords: Z pinning, shear, damage, optical whole-field measurement system, acoustic emission, SEM tensile test

INTRODUCTION

Z pinning consists of inserting composite pins in the laminate in the z-axis. It can be used to prevent delamination in critical laminate zones, such as close to open holes. It is a most promising method to reinforce the out-of-plane properties of prepreg laminates [1-3], but it inevitably reduces the in-plane properties [3-8]. In this work, the influence of Z pins on damage and local strain in composites was tested under in-plane shear. Two types of carbon/epoxy material were studied here: material made by an aeronautical manufacturing process (autoclave), and a marine composite (fabrication under vacuum) in order to evaluate the differences between them.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two materials have been studied, each produced by a different manufacturing method. The reference material, representative of aeronautical production, was produced with unidirectional carbon fibre/epoxy prepreg (IMS/924). 0% and 4% pins were inserted in the plate. The marine composite samples were prepared in a boatyard using Hexcel woven EQ M10/CHS-12k prepreg cured under vacuum. Unpinned and two Z pin densities (2% and 4%) were tested.

An Instron 8803 test machine with a 50 KN load cell was used for all tests according to the ASTM standard D3518M. This involves testing $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens in tension to

determine shear behaviour. An MTS biaxial extensometer and an optical whole-field measurement system (ARAMIS system from GOM GmbH) were used to measure strains. The damage development was studied by acoustic emission (MISTRAS system Euro Physical Acoustic), and tensile testing in a scanning electron microscope.

RESULTS

Modulus variation due to pins

The out of plane reinforcement reduces the in-plane properties. This phenomenon has been studied for 0° and 90° [3,4], and was predicted for 45° composites [5] (9% loss for 2% pins). In our study, the loss was 22% for 4% pins for the aeronautical plate, and up to 50% for 4% pins in the marine composite. The tensile test curve shapes are quite different for the two plates (Figure 1), These differences show that transfer of results from the aircraft to marine industries is not simple. It may be noted that increasing the pin density results in higher standard deviation, Figure 2.

Figure 1. Tensile test plots a) aeronautical b) marine composites

Figure 2. Modulus variation a) aeronautical b) marine composites

Stress variation due to pins

Figure 3 shows $\tau_{12 \max}$ values. These are not the stresses at break, but the values at 5% strain, as specified in the ASTM standard. This value corresponds to 1.5° fibres rotation. The aeronautical panels show considerably higher $\tau_{12 \max}$ values than the marine materials, both with and without pins. The loss is about 12% for both when 4% pins are added.

Figure 3. $\tau_{12 \max}$ variation for 5% strain a) aeronautical b) marine composite

DISCUSSION

Fibre content influence

The pinning increases the laminate thickness. For example, the nautical plate thickness swell from 1.83mm for the unpinned part to 2.30mm for the 4% pinned area. The swelling is known in the literature, it is related to the pins diameter and density [6]. This thickness increase isn't due to material addition, except the pins volume. It is partly due to perpendicular pins insertion, which limit the compaction [8].

Figure 4. Pinned zone

The pinning creates fibre waviness and eye-shaped resin rich zones next to the out-of-plane reinforcement. Craig et al showed that the local waviness could be up to 14° for a 2% pinned zone [4]. It increases linearly with the pin diameter (1° for 0.07mm). Half of the volume of a 4% pinned zone is perturbed by the waviness [6]. The angle between the fibres and the pinning row increases the fibres waviness [6]. Our samples present the maximum angle: 45° .

As noted above, the fibre content is highly perturbed by the pins. In order to subtract a part of this effect, the swelling, the force flux has been studied. Figure 5 and Figure 6 show the stiffness and force fluxes calculated by simply removing the thickness from the usual modulus and stress calculations, as a function of the pin density.

Figure 5. Modulus flux variation for 5% strain as function of the pin density

The modulus slightly decreases for the marine plate with pin density, while the aeronautical plate modulus increases slightly. The force flux increases for both materials. That indicates that the out of plane strengthening acts in a different way for the marine composites.

Figure 6. Force flux modulus variation as function of the pin density

The stress decrease noted in Figure 3 is not visible on the force flux plot above, which indicates that the reduction is due to the thickness increase. This swelling is not caused by material addition, except for the pins. This observation is confirmed by the rupture properties. For the aeronautical samples, the unpinned part breaks with a load flux equal

to 170N mm^{-1} , whereas the 4% pinned part breaks with a load flux equal to 195N mm^{-1} . For the marine composite, which wasn't pinned over all the surface, the fracture never appeared in the pinned area even when the tensile test grip was close to the pinned zone. This can be explained by the delamination phenomenon which appears during the test, and whose propagation was blocked by the out of plane strengthening [1].

Both stress gradient and the flux gradient decrease with the pins content. The literature gives several explanations:

- The fibres waviness, as mentioned previously. This variation is not symmetric nor limited to the plane. The pins are not inserted perpendicularly to the laminate [3,4,6,8].
- Eye shape resin rich region [3,4,6,8].
- Fibre damage due to the pinning [5]
- Compaction variations.

In our samples, the UD laminates are not aligned with the pins rows. This particularity limits the formation of continuous resin channels [8]. Furthermore, the modulus is less affected than cited in [3-5] because the pins allow a higher shear which increases the stiffness [5].

Full field strain analysis

The $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test full field strain is heterogeneous at a local scale [9]. We checked that the average strain obtained by this technique is equal to the value given by a bi-axial extensometer. The strain field depend on the strengthening geometry. The maximum strain is parallel to the fibres (Figure 7) for 2D composites. Figure 8 shows a composite with two distinct zones: an unpinned zone and a 4% pinned zone. The strain field is highly heterogeneous; the unpinned field in the upper part of the picture and in the lower part, the pinned area where the strain is lower and more uniform. This clearly illustrates the influence of the pins on the strain field.

Figure 7. 4% strain for a marine composite (ϵ_{11})

In order to characterize these observations, the average strain is plotted versus the local strain standard deviation for the aeronautical plate (Figure 9). This parameter describes the strain heterogeneity. For the 3D laminate, the strain was measured in the pinned region only. For both composites, the relation between the strain and the standard deviation presents an exponential trend, but the values are lower for the pinned composite. For a 4% global strain, the standard deviation is twice as high for the 2D laminate. This means that the pins homogenise the strain field, perhaps by blocking the fibre rotations.

Figure 8. 5% strain for a 4% de Z pins area and unpinned zone for a marine composite (ϵ_{11})

Figure 9. Average strain versus the strain standard deviation for the aeronautic composite

As the pins influence the strain field it is important to determine whether for pinning used as local strengthening the composite behaves as an unpinned composite for one

region and as a pinned composite for the rest, or if it behaves differently. We compared a standard tensile curve for an unpinned or a pinned composite to a tensile curve made from the unpinned or the pinned zone on a composite which present both regions (ex Figure 8). The thickness used for the stress is the one measured for each part of the sample. The unpinned composite and the unpinned zone curves match together. The same was seen for the pinned area. This means that each zone reacts independently if the pinning is used as local strengthening.

Damage

For the damage study, we worked only with the aeronautical samples. The damage threshold is the first sound localised between two microphones. This characteristic didn't change with the addition of pins, it was recorded at 13 MPa. The acoustic events sum shows a linear trend for both pinned and unpinned composites. The difference comes from the total number of acoustic events recorded, it is higher for the 2D composite.

The acoustic emission energy sum shows the difference between the damage development in the two materials. The plot of this parameter against time for the unpinned composite shows that there are mainly low energy events until the middle of the test. After this point, the sum increases linearly up to the break. The same plot for the pinned composite shows a different trend after the first fifth of the test. During the second fifth of the test, the damage energy sum increases strongly, and then it rises in a linear way up to failure.

The non-summed acoustic emission energy gives some more details about the previous results (Figure 10). For the unpinned composites, most events show low energy. After the middle of the experiment, some high energy events appear in addition to the low energy ones. For the pinned composite, the 3 damage zones clarify the previous graph. The curve first fifth presents the same low energy events as the unpinned sample. During the second fifth, some high energy events are recorded in addition to the previous ones. During the third damage period, the low energy threshold increases. The 3 energy zones correspond to 3 damage modes. All the observations performed in terms of energy can be performed in the same way with the amplitude graph.

The definition of a damage phenomenon by precise parameter intervals is controversial in the literature. We will limit the discussion to the tendencies frequently proposed:

- Low amplitude event: matrix damage
- Medium amplitude event: decohesion damage
- High amplitude event: failure and fibre failure

The damage begins in the same way for both composites, low energy and low amplitude. This is matrix damage, which is why the damage thresholds are equal. The differences start in the second damage zone for the 3D composite. It presents high energy and high amplitude events. In situ tensile tests in the MEB were used to identify mechanisms during this damage period. The SEM pictures show matrix failure in the pins for these loads, Figure 11. During all the high energy events period, some cracks appear in the pins. The cracks are always perpendicular to the tensile force, which means that pin damage is transverse cracking

Figure 10 Energy variation a) unpinned composite b) pinned

. After this second damage zone, the SEM pictures show some crack propagation, but no more crack initiation. For the third damage zone, the amplitude threshold rises. That probably means that the damage which involved the matrix becomes debonding. It can be interfacial, interlaminar or pin-composite debonding. The SEM pictures show some intralaminar cracks which, from time to time, connect to cracks in the pins. It shows some pin debonding and some delamination at the test end. Z pins cannot block the delamination initiation, but strongly influence its propagation [1-3]. The damage change from matrix to debonding is due to blocking of the fibre rotation by the pins as seen previously.

Figure 11 Pin cracking, tests in SEM.

For the unpinned composites, the damage during the first half of the test are low energy and amplitude, as the beginning of the test for the pinned sample, which are matrix damages. For the second half, some medium to high amplitude and energy are recorded, which are debonding damage and fracture. This is attributed to the start of delamination and interface rupture. The matrix damage continues during this part of the test.

CONCLUSION

In this work, the in-plane shear behaviour and damage of composites strengthened by Zpins has been studied. We compare two types of composites, one aeronautical and one marine. The process influences the properties. The pins reduce the in-plane properties, as was previously reported in the literature for other fibre orientations. A 20% to 50% decrease was measured for the modulus for 4% pins. This loss is due to the fibre waviness, resin rich zones, and the compaction modified close to the pins.

A 12% stress loss was noted for the 4% pinned composites. This is an artefact due to the swelling, which is superior to the material addition and which can be attributed to the limited compaction near the pins. If the local thickness is not taken into account, no stress loss is measured. There is then a 5% increase in the force flux for 5% strain, and up to 14% for the force flux at break for composites with 4% pins.

The damage begins in the same way for both composites (pinned and unpinned), by matrix damage above 14MPa. The difference between the 2D and 3D starts for $\tau = 20\text{MPa}$. This corresponds to the stress at which crack initiation starts transverse to the pins. After this initiation, the cracks propagate and the global 3D composite damage changes from matrix damage to debonding (interfacial, pins-matrix, intralaminar...). The pins prevent the delamination up to the very end of the test. The 2D composite damage is matrix damage (as the beginning) with some debonding.

If the pins are used as local strengthening, they would reduce the delamination propagation, without influencing the strengthened area. This increase in out of plane properties would be accompanied by a small modulus loss.

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